

Mobile target acquisition system:

Apollon

Documentation

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Abstract

Technical documentation of the system, including hardware structure, software architecture and operating instructions.

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1 Introduction

1.1 Aim of the project

With the Apollon mobile target acquisition system, targets at long distances of up to 1000 m can be aimed at quickly and effortlessly. The shooter aims directly at the selected target and presses the 'Set' button. Pressing this button stores all the required data, such as the target distance and the tilt angle. The information is sent to a PC, tablet or similar device via Bluetooth. The software calculates the exact position of the target and the ideal launch angle. The angle is transmitted to the system immediately after the calculation. The built-in hardware continuously checks the angle of inclination of the firearm. When the firing angle is reached, the crosshair illumination of the sight is activated and the shooter can release the shot.

The system enables a precise shot pattern at long ranges without having to adjust the sight manually.

1.2 Advantages of the system

In manual operation, the complete processing of the shot preparation process chain takes 30 to 120 seconds. This time span results from the sequential processing of individual sub-steps: visual target identification, manual range measurement (by laser rangefinder or Mil-Dot calculation), consultation of ballistic tables and mechanical adjustment of elevation and windage settings on the sight. Additional delays are caused by necessary recalibrations due to varying environmental conditions (wind, temperature, air pressure) or target movements. The Apollon mobile target acquisition system completes these steps fully automatically in just a few seconds.

In manual mode, targets with widely diverging distances require readjustment, as the sight is mechanically adjusted with every shot.

The automatic sight does not adjust this mechanically, so that the absolute centering is always maintained. This makes it possible to switch quickly from shots at long range to targets at close range.

1.3 Ballistic curve

The ballistic curve provides the basis for the software calculations. The calculation based on the throwing parabola would lead to gross uncertainties. A detailed derivation of the ballistic curve can be found in the book *Die mathematische Theorie ballistischer Kurven* [1]. The following is a brief summary of the chapter "Classical ballistics with air resistance".

The differential equation of the trajectory curve is

$$y''' = 2k\sqrt{1 + y'^2}y'' \quad (1.1)$$

These initial conditions apply:

$$y(0) = 0 \quad (1.2)$$

$$y'(0) = \tan(\theta) \quad (1.3)$$

$$y''(0) = -\frac{g}{v_0^2}\sec(\theta)^2 \quad (1.4)$$

It can be seen that it is no longer an algebraic problem after integrating the differential equation once.

The ballistic coefficient k has an inverse length as a dimension.

$$k = \frac{1}{2} c_w (M) \frac{A \rho_{Luft}}{m} \quad (1.5)$$

Where A is the cross-sectional area of the projectile, ρ_{Luft} is the air density, m is the mass of the projectile and c_w is the drag coefficient. The drag coefficient is very difficult to determine. It is usually determined experimentally. In this project, it only plays a subordinate role.

1.4 Technical overview block diagram

The concept is visualized in Figure 1.1. Where LRF stands for Laser Rangefinder, MPU for Inertial Measurement Unit and MCU for Microcontroller Unit.

Figure 1.1: Block diagram of technical structure

2 Hardware

2.1 Component list

Component	Part Description	Manufacturer
Mikrocontroller	Nano RP2040 Connect	Arduino
Acceleration sensor	6-axis IMU	Arduino
Rangefinder	MINI4-1000m	Nohawk
BMS	Typ-C 15W 3A	***
Battery	18650 9800 mAh	***
Voltage converter	DC-DC Buck Converter	Good Luck Electronic

2.2 Data communication protocols

The MPU sensor communicates via an I2C bus. The connection is made via the SDA (Serial Data Line) connection and the SCL (Serial Clock Line) connection of the microprocessor. The data is transmitted via the SDA interface. The SCL interface is used for clock synchronization. The LRF sensor is controlled via a serial interface. Data can be sent to the sensor via the TX (Transmit) connection. The data can be received via the RX (Receive) connection.

2.2.1 Connection of the LRF sensor

Sensor output	Contact color	Connection on the MCP
RX	green	RX (A1)
TX	yellow	TX (A0)
V_{in}	red	Externes V_{out+}
GND	black	Externes V_{out+} and GND!!

2.3 Circuit diagram

The prototype is set up as shown in circuit diagram 2.1. Two LEDs are connected in parallel to the optical output for simple fault analysis. As the LRF sensor has a current consumption of up to 3 A, it is supplied with power directly from the battery.

Figure 2.1: Apollon circuit diagram

2.4 Prototype construction

As shown in Figure 2.2, the electronics are installed on a breadboard. A frame made of wood can be mounted on the visor so that the breadboard can be attached parallel to the visor. This setup is not ideal, as it is very difficult to align the sensors perfectly horizontally. For easy operation of the system, the release button is mounted above the trigger. This allows the shooter to trigger Apollon without removing his hand from the firing position.

Figure 2.2: Prototype above

Figure 2.3: Prototype assembly sideways

3 Software

3.1 Transmitter-side software

Figure 3.1: Block diagram of transmitter-side software

In the initialization section, the Bluetooth characteristics are defined first. The outputs of the microprocessor are also defined. The following array is defined for communication with the LMR sensor.

Listing 3.1: Example code Sensor communication

```
1 const uint_8 CMD_SINGLE[8] = { 0xAE, 0xA7, 0x00, 0x05, 0x09, 0xBC, 0xBE }
```

The setup function establishes the serial connections to the LMR and the I2C connection to the MPU. If this is successful, a Bluetooth connection is established. A loop continuously checks whether the button has been pressed or not. If it is not pressed, the loop is repeated. When pressed, both sensors are read out and sent. As the current position is sent permanently (for later extensions), the current angles are marked. The angles are calculated as follows:

$$\text{pitch} = \text{atan2}(x, \sqrt{y^2 + z^2}) \cdot \frac{180}{\pi} \quad (3.1)$$

$$\text{roll} = \text{atan2}(y, z) \cdot \frac{180}{\pi} \quad (3.2)$$

$$\text{atan2} = \begin{cases} \arctan\left(\frac{y}{x}\right) & ; x > 0 \\ \arctan\left(\frac{y}{x}\right) + \pi & ; x < 0, y \geq 0 \\ \arctan\left(\frac{y}{x}\right) - \pi & ; x < 0, y < 0 \\ +\frac{\pi}{2} & ; x = 0, y > 0 \\ -\frac{\pi}{2} & ; x = 0, y < 0 \\ \text{undefined} & ; x = 0, y = 0 \end{cases} \quad (3.3)$$

The atan2 offers some advantages over the atan. Only the pitch angle is required for the current calculation. Figure 3.2 shows the pitch angle in relation to the overall arrangement. The roll angle is shown in Figure 3.3.

Figure 3.2: pitch - angel

Figure 3.3: roll - angel

Before the command for the individual measurement is sent to the LMR, the serial buffer is emptied to prevent complications. The `readFrameAndNotify` function is then called. It processes the sensor response and interprets it.

Listing 3.2: `readFrameAndNotify()`

```

1 bool readFrameAndNotify() {
2   unsigned long start = millis();      //Start of the time measurement
3   while (millis() - start < TIMEOUT_MS) {
4     if (Serial1.available() < 3) continue;
5     if (Serial1.read() != 0xAE) continue;    //Check start byte 1
6     if (Serial1.read() != 0xAE) continue;    //Check start byte 2
7
8     uint8_t len = Serial1.read();           //Length of the payload
9
10    uint8_t payload[32];
11    for(uint_t i = 0; i < len; ++i){
12      unsigned long t0 = millis();
13      while(!Serial1.available()){
14        if(millis() - t0 >= TIMEOUT_MS) return false;
15      }
16      payload[i] = Serial1.read();n         //save data
17    }
18    while (Serial1.available()) {
19      if (Serial1.read() == 0xBE) break;     //wait for the end byte
20    }
21    if (payload[1] != 0x85) continue;
22    int16_t raw = (int16_t)((payload[4] << 8) | payload[5]);
23    uint8_t unit = payload[20];
24    if (unit != 0x01) return false;
25    float dist = raw * 0.1f;
26    char str[20];
27    sprintf(str, sizeof(str), "DIST:%.2f", dist);    //send data
28    distanceCharacteristic.writeValue(str);
29    return true;
30  }
31  return false;
32 }

```

A runtime measurement checks whether complications occur during reading. The system waits for both start bytes to be sent. The start bytes are followed by a byte that specifies the length of the payload. The data bytes are read until the end byte is recognized. Once reading is complete, a 16-bit raw value is extracted. The raw value is scaled with the corresponding unit of measurement. This value is then sent to the receiver via the BLE connection.

As soon as the receiver has calculated the launch angle, it is received and interpreted by the on-CommandWritten function.

Listing 3.3: onCommandWritten()

```

1 void onCommandWritten(BLEDevice central, BLECharacteristic characteristic) {
2   const uint8_t* rawData = characteristic.value();
3   int len = characteristic.valueLength();
4   char cmd[len + 1];
5   memcpy(cmd, rawData, len);
6   cmd[len] = '\0'; // zero - terminate
7   BLE.poll();
8
9   if (strncmp(cmd, "THRESH:", 7) == 0) {
10    pitchThreshold = atof(cmd + 7);
11  }
12 }

```

The launch angle is saved as pitchThreshold. An if condition checks in the main loop whether the launch angle is reached. A permitted deviation has been set to 0.1° . As soon as the launch angle is within the permitted range, the optical output is activated.

The calculations on the transmitter side have been reduced to a minimum to ensure fast processing of the data.

3.2 Receiver-side software

Figure 3.4: Block diagram of receiver-side software

The Bluetooth connection is maintained permanently. As soon as the marked angle and the measured distance have been sent, these are interpreted by the handle-notify and handle-notify-distance functions. These values are saved as variables. The calculation of the launch angle is performed by the calculate-with-trajectory function. The function is divided into two parts. In the first part, the parameters are defined and the basic calculations are carried out.

Listing 3.4: berechnung-mit-trajectora Parameters

```

1 pitch_offset = math.radians(theta_LS_pitch)
2 x_target = distanz * math.cos(pitch_offset)
3 h_target = distanz * math.sin(pitch_offset)

```

Theta-LS-picht is the angle of the current position, it is converted into radians. As the measured distance describes a hypotenuse of a right-angled triangle, the position of the target can be determined exactly using the Pythagorean theorem. The horizontal distance from the system to the target is stored in the variable x-target and the vertical distance in the variable h-target.

Listing 3.5: calculation-with-trajectora

```

1 def simulate_height(angle_rad: float):
2     vx = v * math.cos(angle_rad)
3     vy = v * math.sin(angle_rad)
4     x = 0.0
5     y = 0.0
6     while x < x_target:
7         v_tot = math.hypot(vx, vy)
8         if v_tot == 0:
9             break
10        a_drag = 0.5 * rho * cd * A * v_tot**2 / m
11        ax = -a_drag * (vx / v_tot)
12        ay = -g - a_drag * (vy / v_tot)
13        vx += ax * dt
14        vy += ay * dt
15        x += vx * dt
16        y += vy * dt
17        return y - h_target
18    low, high = -math.pi/4, math.pi/4
19    f_low = simulate_height(low)
20    f_high = simulate_height(high)
21    if f_low * f_high > 0:
22        raise ValueError("Keine Loesung im realistischen Winkelbereich gefunden.")
23
24    launch_angle = None
25    for _ in range(max_iter):
26        mid = 0.5 * (low + high)
27        f_mid = simulate_height(mid)
28        if abs(f_mid) < tol:
29            launch_angle = mid
30            break
31        if f_low * f_mid < 0:
32            high, f_high = mid, f_mid
33        else:
34            low, f_low = mid, f_mid
35    if launch_angle is None:
36        launch_angle = mid # Emergency solution
37
38    # Final simulation for plot
39    vx = v * math.cos(launch_angle)
40    vy = v * math.sin(launch_angle)
41    x_vals = [0.0]
42    y_vals = [0.0]
43    while x_vals[-1] < max_range:
44        v_tot = math.hypot(vx, vy)
45        if v_tot == 0:
46            break
47        a_drag = 0.5 * rho * cd * A * v_tot**2 / m
48        ax = -a_drag * (vx / v_tot)
49        ay = -g - a_drag * (vy / v_tot)

```

```

50     vx += ax * dt
51     vy += ay * dt
52     x_vals.append(x_vals[-1] + vx * dt)
53     y_vals.append(y_vals[-1] + vy * dt)
54     if x_vals[-1] > max_range:
55         break
56
57     return x_vals, y_vals, launch_angle, x_target, h_target

```

The optimum launch angle is found in the simulate-high function using a simulation. The velocity is broken down into its x and y components and the starting point is set at $x=0$ and $y=0$. The current position in the y direction is determined in a while loop, taking into account the air resistance and the acceleration due to gravity. From this, the vertical deviation from the target position can be determined. The simulation runs until the optimum launch angle between -45° and 45° is found. This interval offers the best efficiency, as the maximum range of a projectile is achieved at an angle of 45° . If no angle is found, an error message is displayed. In a final simulation with the angle found, the position values are saved so that the trajectory can be plotted 3.5.

Figure 3.5: Benutzer- Ausgabe

Figure 3.5 shows the user output. This is where the user can start the system. Current status messages such as received angle, measured distance and launch angle can be read there. The exact position of the target is marked in a plot and the optimum flight path is entered.

4 System test

4.1 Test setup

The Apollon system was set up as described in chapter 2. . The test is carried out with a Hex 400 crossbow. This is particularly suitable for this test, as the crossbow has a very pronounced ballistic trajectory. In order to obtain comparable characteristics with a large-calibre firearm, it would be necessary to shoot at several hundred meters. The crossbow has a launch energy of 286 J. This energy is comparable to the launch energy of a .22 caliber lfB pistol. However, the crossbow also has some inaccuracies. The sight used is not precisely averaged, so that there is always a systematic deviation of up to 5 cm. A 15 cm x 15 cm target is aimed at.

4.2 Test procedure

Due to the terrain, it is not possible to maintain exactly the same firing height. The first shot is taken at a distance of 42.4 m. The shot was taken just above the target with a deviation from the center line of 8 cm. The horizontal deviation from the center of the target is negligible. The hit can be seen in Figure 4.1. The software runs on a laptop that can be connected to the system via Bluetooth. The calculated trajectory is shown in Figure 4.2. The target was approx. 2 m below the launch point.

Figure 4.1: Hit at 42m

Figure 4.2: Hit at 42m User output

The second shot was fired from a distance of 69.7 m, which is also the limit of the test site. A hit was also made at this distance. The deviation from the target line is 20cm 4.3. At this distance, the ballistic curve is very pronounced, which is particularly evident in the calculated angle difference. The angle determined during target acquisition was -1.78° and the calculated launch angle was 0.44° 4.4. These values result in an angle difference $\Delta = 2,21^\circ$.

Figure 4.3: Hit at 69.7m

Figure 4.4: Hit at 69.7m User output

4.3 Evaluation

The system test has shown that the system works very well. The deviations are due to the non-ideal phototype setup. The poor sighting contributes to a large part of the deviations, as these lead to inaccuracies in target acquisition. It has been shown that the exact positioning of the range sensor is very important. In this setup, the position of the LRF is not ideal, which also leads to deviations. If the result is considered in relation to the non-ideal setup, the result is very impressive.

5 Further development

This project has impressively demonstrated the enormous potential of a mobile target acquisition system. Using the Apollon system, even an inexperienced shooter can accurately hit targets at long range - a result that would otherwise require years of practice.

The next step in the further development of the project would be the construction of a suitable housing to enable the sensors to be positioned precisely and stably. Equally crucial is the integration of a high-quality sight to further improve aiming accuracy.

The integrated IMU sensor provides precise position data in all spatial directions. In future, this data could also be used to take horizontal influences such as crosswinds into account. In addition, the shot fired can be analyzed in more detail by systematically evaluating the position and acceleration data.

Bibliography

- [1] Eugen Willerding. *Die mathematische Theorie ballistischer Kurven*. Eugen Willerding, 2020.